

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Models to predict late blight: a sustainable strategy to reduce the use of pesticides on potato crop

Late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) is the most destructive disease of potato worldwide. Its control is based on the application of fungicides following pre-established schedules. However, in recent years, the European Commission has approved the Green Deal and the “Farm to Fork” strategy, which aims to reduce pesticide use by 50% by 2030. In this sense, the objective of this research was to apply a prediction model in potato cultivation in A Limia (NW-Spain) with the aim of controlling late blight with the minimum use of fungicides considering meteorological variables. The Kennebec cultivar was planted in three subplots called Control (without fungicides), conventional (with applications every 7-10 days) and Decision support system (according to the NegFry model (Ullrich & Schrödter, 1966 and Fry et al., 1983, Hansen et al., 1995). A

weather station was installed for this purpose. Disease progress was also observed weekly and the r-AUDPC was calculated according to Fry (1978). In 2021 and 2022, 6 and 7 fungicide treatments were applied in the conventional subplot while in the decision support system subplot there were 3 in both years and none in the control subplot. As for the damage caused by *P. infestans*, this was 0% and 1% in 2021 and 2022 respectively in the conventional plot and 1% in both years in the plot treated according to the decision support system. In contrast, the control plot had 47.5% disease in 2021 and 1% in 2022. In view of the results obtained, betting on predictive models for the control of late blight can be a useful and profitable strategy for farmers and respectful and sustainable for the environment and agricultural systems of the present and future.

1. In the picture could be observed in the three subplots considered for the study: Control (without fungicides); Routine (fungicides applied every 7 days), and the plot treated according to a Decision Support System (DSS).

KEYWORDS

Solanum tuberosum, *Phytophthora infestans*, Decision Support System, sustainable management

AUTHORSHIP

Laura Meno Fariñas, Universidade de Vigo (UVigo), Vigo, Spain.
Olga Escuredo Pérez, Universidade de Vigo (UVigo), Vigo, Spain.
Carmen Seijo Coello, Universidade de Vigo (UVigo), Vigo, Spain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

This factsheet is produced as part of the SoildiverAgro project. Although the author has worked on the best information available, neither the author nor the EU shall in any event be liable for any loss, damage or injury incurred directly or indirectly in relation to the project.